

QUANTIFICATION OF HYPERSPECTRAL PLANES EFFECTIVENESS - A SEMANTIC SEGMENTATION PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Automatic monitoring of agricultural crops with remote sensing data allows significant improvement in the face of climate change and environmental degradation. Hyperspectral imaging supports this process with spectrally detailed data, which goes beyond visible spectrum. In this paper we investigate how much information is actually brought by the richness and the details of additional spectral information. The assumed perspective is that of agricultural crop semantic segmentation approached with a powerful visual transformer based solution. Into more detail, we explore the effectiveness of various spectral bands in hyperspectral images, used as input, measured by five metrics quantifying the performance of agricultural crop segmentation. The evaluation relies on the UAV-HSI database. The primary conclusion is that there is significant redundancy in hyperspectrum, yet the full spectrum provides always top results. A secondary conclusion is that the recognition of specific crops such as “cotton” and “holly” benefits from removal of certain bands.

Keywords— remote sensing, crop segmentation, visual transformer, ranking, spectrum bands

1 Introduction

A¹ remarkable transformations in today’s agriculture is the integration of digitization and artificial intelligence,

¹Preprint. Authoritative version can be followed on IEEEExplore web-site.

by providing a cost-effective alternative to human-made judgments. Digital data from on-site, proximal, and satellite measurements provide valuable insights into crop health and condition. Remote sensing, in particular, offers a powerful source of information by capturing views of fields much larger than what the human eye can observe. For agricultural crops, remote sensing data provides critical insights into growth, vigor, and their dynamics, serving as an objective foundation for both macro and micromanagement of production.

Remote sensing data often comes in the form of multispectral or hyperspectral imaging, allowing for a comprehensive analysis beyond the limits of human perception. Two widely used sources for this data are satellite imaging and Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) imaging.

Satellite-based remote sensing platforms offer data with high spatial, spectral, and temporal resolution, enabling the extraction of consistent and cost-effective long-term data series [1]. Additionally, platforms such as Sentinel-2 and Landsat 7-8, provide free access to visible and multispectral data. However, two main challenges arise for precision agriculture when using satellite data: the per-pixel resolution (10 m for Sentinel, 30 m per pixel for Landsat and 250 m for MODIS) and the orbit period (16 days for Landsat/MODIS, and 12 days for Sentinel-1).

Alternatively, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) have become increasingly widespread in recent years, due to being affordable options with camera payloads ranging from visible to hyperspectral imaging. They typically include fixed-wing or multirotor models and have a limited flight time of around 15 to 25 minutes. Yet, they provide higher spatial and temporal data resolution at sub-meter per-pixel resolution, being more suitable for precision agriculture [1].

Remote sensing imaging captures electromagnetic

wave reflectance from plant canopies. Plants’ reflectance of light (also known as spectral reflectance or emission characteristics) varies due to factors such as plant type and tissue water content, as well as other chemical and morphological properties [2]. Applications focus on the following light spectra: *Ultraviolet* (UV) region: 10 to 380 nm; *Visible* (VIS) spectrum: blue (450-495 nm), green (495-570 nm), and red (620-750 nm); *Near and mid-infrared* (NIR) band: 850-1700 nm.

However a question arises: Is the entire spectra useful and needed for agricultural applications? The plethora of applications [3] suggests an affirmative answer. Yet, one may find, also, indirect negative suggestions. For instance, experts often use vegetation indices (VI) to characterize various aspects of crops and these VI focus on very few bands [4], [5], ignoring the rest. Systematic evaluation of contribution each spectrum band to a specific purpose exists, but was often limited to specific applications. For instance, Peon et al. [6] investigated different type of sensor data efficiency in estimation of carbon residuum in burned areas. The study found that in some cases, narrow-range sensors are more effective than wide-range ones, but the findings relied on the tool utilized, which preferred data with low dimensionality. By integrating various studies, Dian et al. [7] found that combining hyperspectral data with multispectral data yields improved results with respect to either, thus arguing for the value of hyperspectral bands. In front of this evidence, we argue that we need more systematic investigation, before providing definite conclusions.

Our approach assumes a crop semantic segmentation perspective. We argue, first, that semantic segmentation is a highly important step in developing applications for agriculture. We refer to the conclusion of the review conducted by Akbar et al. [8] to provide support. Particular arguments are brought by [9], which use it for monitoring the sowing processes, [10] for pest segmentation. A separate observation is that recent methods are dominated by deep learning approaches [11] or, newer, by Visual Transformers [12].

Here, we assume the following approach. The main task is that of crop semantic segmentation on the UAV-HSI hyperspectral database. We are using a Visual Transformer architecture, that by using the entire spectrum of wavelengths, reaches state of the art performance. Furthermore, we remove certain ranges from the spectrum (either compact, either sparse) and observe the differences in performance. Thus, we connect the contribution of certain wavelength ranges to the crop segmentation efficiency.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the segmentation architecture, summarizes the dataset, and the metrics used to quantify the

Figure 1: G-Cascade model adapted to hyperspectral imaging. The figure is best viewed in digital form, with zoom.

performance. Section 3 presents the results, along with commentary. The paper ends with limitations and conclusions.

2 Method

2.1 Segmentation Model

The segmentation problem is addressed within a deep learning framework utilizing the Cascaded Graph Convolutional Attention Decoder (G-Cascade) architecture [13]. The model, depicted in Figure 1, while employs the typical encoder-decoder structure, it does improve upon previous approaches by progressively refining the multi-stage feature maps generated by hierarchical transformer encoders, and decoding by using an efficient graph convolution block.

Encoder. In the G-Cascade framework, the encoder is built on the Pyramid Vision Transformer architecture [14], which leverages a self-attention mechanism to capture long-range dependencies. The architecture is inspired by the Visual Transformers (ViT) [15] family, treating each image as a series of fixed-length tokens (patches) that are processed by multiple Transformer layers for representation.

Decoder. The G-Cascade model consists of efficient up-convolution blocks (UCBs) for upsampling features, graph convolutional attention modules (GCAMs) to enhance feature maps, and segmentation heads (Seg-Heads) to generate the segmentation output. The model includes four GCAMs, corresponding to the four stages of pyramid features from the encoder. To integrate the multi-scale features, the upsampled features from the previous decoder block are first combined with the features from the skip connections, either through addition or concatenation. These concatenated features

are then processed by the GCAM module to improve semantic information. The output from each GCAM is sent to a prediction head, and finally, the four different prediction maps are aggregated to produce the final segmentation result.

With respect to the G-Cascade architecture, we emphasize the placement of the depth wise convolution, which acts as selector on depth, thus, giving learned importance to planes, including the input hyperspectral ones.

The training loss function is a linear combination of pixel-based cross-entropy and image-based Dice coefficient.

For specific and precise details, we kindly ask the reader to follow the introductory paper [13]. The most significant modification is re-adjusting the input layer to accommodate hyperspectral images. The model has been used in fine-tuning regime, with initial weights computed on ImageNet[13].

2.2 Dataset

The dataset used in this project, UAV-HSI [12], is publicly available² and includes two sub-regions: Makialou Village’s plots (MJK_N, MJK_S) and Xijingmeng Village’s plots (XJM). The hyperspectral data was collected on September 18th, 2019, using an electric helicopter. The UAV was equipped with a Pika L hyperspectral sensor from Resonon, capturing 200 bands across a spectral range of 385nm to 1034nm. The dataset is pixel-level annotated with 30 unevenly distributed classes. Further details on the acquisition equipment can be found in the accompanying article [12].

Building on the initial work [12], the dataset is pre-organized into training and testing subsets. Each image is composed of 96×96 pixels with 200 spectral bands, and the labels correspond to categories ranging from 1 to 30, representing different vegetation classes. As shown in Figure 3, the crop distribution is uneven. The meaning of the spectral bands is detailed in both the introductory paper and the camera manual.

2.3 Segmentation quality metrics

Our purpose is to accurately quantify the performance of various alternatives for semantic segmentation. To achieve this, a package of several established metrics will be used. Given that the database contains data from 30 classes, first the confusion matrix, having elements c_{ii} , is computed from pixel accuracy. Then the following measures derive:

²The dataset can be downloaded at: <https://www.scidb.cn/en/detail?dataSetId=6de15e4ec9b74dacab12e29cb557f041>

1. Overall accuracy (OA) and Kappa coefficient :

$$OA = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^C c_{ii} \quad (1)$$

$$Kappa = \frac{N \sum_i^C c_{ii} - N \sum_i^C (c_{i+} \cdot c_{+i})}{N^2 - \sum_i^C (c_{i+} \cdot c_{+i})} \quad (2)$$

where $C = 30$ is the number of classes and the row length, c_{ii} are the diagonal (correct) elements, c_{i+} and c_{+i} represents the sum of the elements in the row and respectively the columns where c_i is located.

2. Intersection over Union - (IoU), per class:

$$IoU_c = \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FP_c + FN_c} \quad (3)$$

where TP_c is the true positives, FP_c is the false positives, and FN_c is the false negatives for a class c . To aggregate on the database, the average of IoU over class is considered.

3. Dice score, defined as:

$$DSC(Y, \hat{Y}) = \frac{2 \times |Y \cap \hat{Y}|}{|Y| + |\hat{Y}|} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where Y and \hat{Y} are the ground truth and, respectively, the predicted segmentation map, per image.

4. 95% Hausdorff Distance (D_{H95}) which is the greatest of all the distances from a point in the ground truth set Y to the closest point in predicted segmentation map \hat{Y} and formally defined as:

$$D_{H95} = \max\{\max_{y \in Y} \min_{\hat{y} \in \hat{Y}} d(y, \hat{y}), \max_{\hat{y} \in \hat{Y}} \min_{y \in Y} d(y, \hat{y})\} \quad (5)$$

In this case, only, smaller values are better.

3 Results

Implementation. The method has been implemented in Python using PyTorch support for deep learning. On a computer having an A4000 GPU, the training of the full dataset, for 100 epochs takes about 24 hours. The inference requires 2.4 seconds for a full hyperspectral image from the dataset.

Baseline. To anchor the test, we first report the performance when using all the planes. This test of the architecture strength is passed as G-Cascade leads to state of the art performance, when compared to the previous results, the most notable being that of Niu et al. [12], which used an adapted TransUNet architecture. These may be followed in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparative performance on the UAV-
HSI database. For D_{H95} metric better is lower,
while for the rest better is higher

Architectures/Loss	Dice[%]	D_{H95}	OA[%]	Kappa
TransUNet - CE [12]	n/a	n/a	78.64	0.7456
HSL-TransUNet - CE+Dice [12]	n/a	n/a	86.05	0.8347
TransUNet - CE+Dice (us)	87.15	7.12	83.25	0.812
G-Cascade - CE +Dice (us)	90.87	4.15	86.56	0.8399

Table 2: Crop segmentation when a part of the
original spectrum has been removed. The perfor-
mance is averaged for all classes, while crop based
performance is in figure 2

Removed range	Dice[%]	D_{H95}	IoU[%]	OA[%]	Kappa
None	90.87	4.15	91.95	86.56	0.840
385 nm - 514.8 nm	85.75	5.43	86.16	71.69	0.661
514.8 nm - 644.6 nm	90.12	5.36	90.37	79.21	0.753
644.6 nm - 774.4 nm	91.2	4.71	91.48	84.44	0.815
774.4 nm - 904.2 nm	90.3	5.32	90.65	78.96	0.746
904.2 nm - 1034 nm	86.91	5.17	87.23	74.87	0.702

Removing compact ranges. To view the contribution of various parts of the spectrum, we divided the set of 200 planes into 5 compact ranges of 40 planes. For each such case (i.e. removing a range), we have trained the network over the entire training set, but having images with 160 bands and evaluated the performance. In this test, if the removal leads to increase that part is detrimental, while largest decrease identifies parts of spectrum that contribute more. The aggregated results may be seen in Table 2, while performance for each of the 30 classes may be seen in Figure 2.

With respect to aggregated results, the best performance is using all bands. The most damage was done by removing the UV part followed by the NIR-Red. The first is surprising, while the later is accordance with prior work, that emphasizes the role of NIR in constructing the NDVI index. Also rather surprisingly, is that by removal of center of the visible spectrum (green-yellow) part, little harm is done; we argue that while “green” is definitory for plants, they all have it and little discrimination is possible there.

One point of emphasis is that the variation of change is different in magnitude given the segmentation metric used, thus arguing for the necessity of using multiple metrics.

Another point of discussion is the relative frequency of a crop in the database, as some have very little presence and are not segmented correctly at all. Yet to place in the proper context, the change of accuracy per crop is in Figure 3. A general observation is that major differences can be seen for crops that are less present, suggesting limitations due to database. Overall, for many crops, there is little variance, for some there is visi-

Table 3: Crop segmentation when a only a part of
the original spectrum has been kept. The removal
is over all bands, keeping only every N -th band

Bands kept	Dice[%]	D_{H95}	IoU[%]	OA[%]	Kappa
All	90.87	4.15	91.95	86.56	0.840
Every 2nd	90.01	4.41	90.41	81.53	0.782
Every 5th	90.03	4.17	90.80	81.78	0.783
Every 10th	90.02	4.65	90.06	80.58	0.771

ble decrease and for few (“cotton”, “sesame”, “holly”) there is an increase.

Using sparse ranges. A second set of tests investigated the redundancy in neighboring planes. The hypothesis is that nearing bands are highly correlated and, thus, redundant. For this scenario, instead of removing a compact range of spectrum, we only kept every N -th band from the hyperspectrum. The results may be followed in Table 3. Removal of bands reduces the performance, but with surprisingly small quanta given the amount of removal.

4 Limitations. Conclusions

While in the approached procedure we did not assume any limiting hypothesis, yet the results are dependent on database specifics, with an emphasis on existing crops and on used hyperspectral camera (Resonon Pika L).

With respect to conclusions, we have found out that: (i) In general, using the full spectrum provides the best overall results. (ii) Removing parts of the spectrum, the recognition of specific crops, such as “cotton” (removing yellow), “holly” (removing blue-violet) or “scallion” is improved; here, we hypothesize that in that range, the signature of the crop is very similar to another one, bringing confusion. (iii) Removing sparse parts of the hyperspectrum, the performance decreases, but with rather surprisingly small margins considering the amount of removal (up to 90% - decrease up to 5% only); this suggest that, specifically, for crop semantic segmentation, wider aggregate bands may be more beneficial. (iv) For the majority of crops, the use of all hyperspectral bands leads to top performance or to very minor changes; for certain crops, such as “sorghum”, “kohlrabi”, “peanut”, band removal has catastrophic results in separation. However, the overall performance does not place strong emphasis on the need of crop-based band selection.

Figure 2: Per crop accuracies [%] when certain spectral compact ranges have been removed from the full spectrum. We tried to represent each test with **dominant color** that has been **removed**. The first bar (dark gray) is the baseline - full spectrum.

Acknowledgment

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Figure 3: Distribution of crop pixels in UAV-HSI database marked with blue and the deviation (variability) of the recognition rates when compact wavelength ranges have been removed. For each bar, the number represents the standard deviation

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